

THE COMPLEXITY OF FEMALE EXPERIENCE IN A PATRIARCHAL SOCIETY:
"SENSE AND SENSIBILITY" BY JANE AUSTEN

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Abstract: *This article highlights the issues of gender inequality and social stratification presented in "Sense and sensibility". Jane Austen (1775-1817) vividly depicted her critical views about economic and interpersonal boundaries in a society. She tried to define societal pressure, Women's financial dependence on men and classism in her satirical World. While Austen primarily emphasized the patriarchy of the 19th century, she adeptly encouraged women to fight for their own rights and freedom, to receive an education, and to achieve economic independence. This article also illustrates construction between relying on intelligence and following emotions through the lives of Dashwood sisters, Elinor and Marianne, who had different personalities in the story*

Keywords: *gender inequality, social stratification, interpersonal boundaries, patriarchy, economic independence, intelligence, Emotions.*

Introduction: Jane Austen played a vital role in the development of modern literature through her realistic novels filled with irony and satire. In the 19th century, women's rights were severely restricted; girls were often raised with the purpose of marriage, and their opinions were largely ignored. As female writers were not allowed to publish their works under their own names, Jane Austen published her novels anonymously. Therefore, she promoted the limitation of male-dominated society and inspired woman to have their own personal domain.

Austen's novel *Sense and Sensibility* not only has its share of romantic events, but also serves to show the significance of the emotions and social independence of women. In addition, it addresses how both logical reasoning and emotional thinking through the contrasting examples of the two main characters, Elinor and Marianne Dashwood, affect the complexity of people's decisions. While Elinor exemplifies "sense" by being able to repress her emotions, controlling her emotional responses, and making her life decisions based on rational thought; Marianne is an example of "sensibility" by responding emotionally to most

of the events in her life throughout the story. The differences in the ways that Elinor and Marianne respond to life's events are similar to the experience of both Colonel Brandon and Edward Ferrars and demonstrate how the external forces of society's values and norms determine the lives of individuals. By highlighting the dichotomy between personal feelings and social norms through these four central characters, Austen provides important commentary regarding the balance of the two in everyday life.

“Fortunately Austen outgrew these ideas, and *Sense and Sensibility* is her only novel that has so much in common with typically eighteenth-century narratives”(Diane Shubinsky,1999).This story is written in an omniscient style. More precisely, the events that occur in it are narrated in the third person, and the writer reveals the feelings and thoughts of each character. An example of this is how Elinor controls her emotions and how she supports her family in financial difficulties.

Literary review

Gender imbalance between men and woman has always been a controversial topic. Feminist novelist such as Jane Austen, Wirginia Woolf, Charlotte Perkins illustrated the dominance of men, inferiority towards woman during 18th and 19th century through their works. According to Julia Edo Larraz(2015)"The victim of this masculine pride were always women". At that time, women were deprived of education, work, and governance, while men saw themselves as the sole rulers of society and hid their feelings. Wollstonecraft's claimed that women are not naturally inferior to men, but what makes the former appear like that is the lack of education. She proposes that both sexes should be treated as equal rational beings – being the rights of men and of women the same thing “(Jullia,2015). Jane Austen was inspired by Wollstonecraft's ideas about women's education and their role in society, as a result, in her works "Sense and Sensibility" and "Pride and Prejudice", she portrayed girls as intelligent, witty, and able to control their emotions. This portrays that woman also have same abilities with man in terms of intelligence and resilience.

In “Sense and Sensibility” daughters of Dashwood, family could not inherit their father's estate because, during those times, women did not have such rights. They suffered financial hardship as women were prohibited from working and earning money. «Women do not get much inheritance over men and they do not get education so they cannot

make money themselves, they only expect to be married by rich men” (Myta Kusumawardhani & Endang Yuliani Rahayu,2020).

In fact Mrs. Dashwood actually wanted her daughters to marry rich and well-connected men. This was the only way to get the kids out of poverty and other challenges. For example, in the story Charlotte marries Mr. Palmer not for love but for social stability and financial gain. As stated by Weigui Zhou (August 28,2016)“In this patriarchal society, a good marriage, to a middle-class woman, is a marriage of their wealth and their status.”

“Austen encouraged the new ideal of the ‘sober Victorian’ man rather than the ‘Georgian libertine” (Malin Landin,2017). Even though Jane Austen lived before Victorian era, her Novel compered Georgian libertine with Victorian man. Men lived freely during the Georgian libertine period,they put their interest above others and played with the women's emotions. On the other hand Victorian man followed the rules of society, respected women and controlled himself. In the novel, Willoughby represents Georgian libertine because of his selfishness and brutality ,but, Colonel Brandon and Edward Ferrars were true Victorian men because of their responsibility and love.

Methodology

The article analyzes Jane Austen's social novel "Sense and Sensibility" using the literary analysis methodology. The text is closely studied and examined to reveal the main idea of the novel. In addition, «comparative studies are also used by contrasting different characters in the work. This investigation attempts to explain not only the role of women in society, but also current issues such as segregation, gendered economics.

Discussion:

„Sense and sensibility” is timeless novel of Jane Austen that describes the pressing problems of the 18th and 19th centuries including issues in family relationships, social class, injustices against women, and financial difficulties. In Her novel ,she attempts to create realistic phenomena, such as social norms of the society, based on imaginary characters and events. In the first chapter of the book she begins her novel with the problems of inheritance in the Dashwood family.

"It was very well known that no fortune was left to them;... their father had no privilege of altering their destiny." (Chapter 2 p.8)

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Therefore, these lines show that Henry Dashwood's property upon his death went to John rather than his daughters—because at that time, women could not inherit land, and everything went to men. This further illustrates how dependent women were on men and how little liberty they had in the 19th century. For example, in the story, the daughters of the Dashwood family experience great financial hardship after their father's death because they were legally prohibited from bequeathing his estate. Through this scene, Jane Austen illuminate that despite of responsibility and intelligence of the women , they lack financial protection ,revealing gender injustices of the society. Besides, by that message she tried to change people's perspective about moral standards and prevent woman from social inequality and legal injustice.

The story "Sense and Sensibility" compares two different personalities: one who controls her emotions and acts with reason, and the other who is completely guided by feelings. Which character do you support and encourage — reason or emotion?

"I will be calm; I will be mistress of myself" (Chapter 37, p.g130).

In the novel, Elinor represent the embodiment of sense and reason. Through this quote, we can see that Elinor can control herself and her emotions in any situation. Elinor portrayed in the play as a very honest and intelligent person. She also has strong emotions, but she knows how to govern them. She can make any decision not with feelings, but by correctly assessing the situation. However, it is not always right to suppress one's feelings for the benefit of others. As Ina Daril Hanna(2016) said "Elinor was in suffering and heart broken, but she did not want someone know about her suffer furthermore, Lucy». For example, Elinor is forced to keep her feelings bottled up because of Lucy Steele's unrequited love for Edward. She is also compelled to keep secrets due to her obligation towards Lucy, which only increases Elinor's inner pain. Therefore, if a person keeps their pain and feelings repressed for a prolonged duration, it can cause serious psychological damage.

"Marianne's abilities were, in many respects, quite equal to Elinor's. She was sensible and clever; but eager in everything: her sorrows, her joys, could have no moderation. She was generous, amiable, interesting: she was everything but prudent."(Chapter 1, p 6)

Marianne was also a very intelligent and capable girl. However, unlike Elinor, she was very emotional and passionate. Her problem was that she lacked moderation and prudence. "Marianne Dashwood was

born to an extraordinary fate”(Alan Dugald McKillop, 1957).She gave in completely to her emotions, which later left her helpless after Willoughby’s betrayal. Marianne Dashwood falls in love with John Willoughby, a person who put wealth and self-interests over love, and this leads to a very strong emotional blow at the end of the work. Marianne’s eventual love with Colonel Brandon at the end is an example of how she began to rely not only on feelings but also on reason. Moreover, she realizes that love is not only about passion, but also about respect and loyalty.

According to the book 'Sense and Sensibility', an individual must keep a balance between rationality and emotion to be happy in their lives. When either of these elements is used exclusively, the person experiences emotional pain; therefore, combining the two elements creates an individual who experiences a full, balanced life. For example, as both of a bird's wings are needed for flight; individuals cannot engage both reason and emotion to create a fulfilled existence.

"Mrs. Ferrars's resolution that both her sons should marry well, and of the danger attending any young woman who attempted to DRAW HIM IN..."(Chapter 4, p 14)

"Miss Morton is Lord Morton's daughter... she is the person whom we hope to see Edward married to... she has thirty thousand pounds... Her style of painting is quite different. It has so much more spirit and execution."(Chapter 34 p 115-116)

The author Jane Austen uses Mrs. Ferrars as a means to express her opinion on the unfairness and strictness of 19th century society's class system. Mrs. Ferrars is portrayed by Austen as an individual that exemplifies social stratification by valuing money and status over human feelings. For example, when Mrs. Ferrars refuses to accept Elinor Dashwood due to her lack of money, this illustrates the inequity associated with a class system. Furthermore, Mr. Ferrara's attitude towards Elinor suggests that everything is measured in terms of money, and that good qualities in a person are completely ignored.

"But have you likewise heard that Miss Grey has fifty thousand pounds? In that, if in anything, we may find an explanation." (Chapter 30, p 104)

Willoughby marries Miss Grey, not Marrian, because he wants to save his career. This shows that female emotions were insignificant and undervalued in the past. Willoughby did not choose his beloved because

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Miss Grey had 50,000 pounds, which Marrian did not have, and this money would have helped him pay off all his debts and maintain his luxurious life. In this story, it is clear that social norms and the segregation of society impacted the living conditions of people negatively.

"...he had left the girl whose youth and innocence he had seduced, in a situation of the utmost distress, with no other resource from unmerited infamy than that of a death-bed repentance."(Chapter 31, p109)

At fourteen, otherwise healthy and happy, she was placed at a school in Dorset shire... It was there that she was found by Willoughby."(Chapter 31, p108)

Willoughby seduces a 14-year-old girl and causes her to become pregnant. Exploitation of minor was considered a serious offense at both the time and today. This quote does not portray Willoughby as a young and transgressing young man, but as a person with predatory behavior. Society ignored Willoughby's cruelty to a 14-year-old orphan girl because he was a representative of the upper class and prestige, and no one was concerned that a girl's future and life were being ruined. Jane Austen exposes the "double standards" of society through this, because Eliza is a low-class and vulnerable woman, Willoughby takes advantage of her and continues on as if nothing has happened. This relationship shows how men played with women's emotions and treated them as socially inferior, and view girls' vulnerability as a "privilege" during the Jane Austen's era.

Conclusion

By reading Jane Austen's *Sense and Sensibility*, one can understand different lifestyles in English society during 18th and 19th century much better. The work especially shows the role of women in society, their financial dependence and limited opportunities in life. The events that happened to the Dashwood family can be a vivid example as they face financial difficulties after their father's death and could not earn money independently. Therefore, it can often be seen that marriage for women was not only a matter of love, but also a vital necessity.

The work presents two different characters and approaches to life through Elinor and Marianne Dashwood in a very simple but touching way. Elinor is shown as a girl who is restrained, patient and always able to control herself. She does not reveal her feelings to everyone and acts more logically. Marianne, on the other hand, is the opposite - she is very sincere, open and does not hide her feelings. She always acts based on her emotions, which lately cause her to feel pain and to make bad

decisions."Additionally we learn that sense and sensibility are not opposed; the real distinction here is between social and selfish sensibilities".(Inger Sigrun Brodey,2015)

As we read the novel, we gradually understand that it is not right to live only with emotions or only with logic. The right way for a person is to keep these two in balance. Jane Austen also shows this idea through very simple events. The characters grow through the trials they experience, learn from their mistakes, and gradually begin to see life from different perspective. At the same time, she criticizes the role of women in society in an satirical way.The novel clearly shows how women's dependence on men in many aspects of life and the limited choices available to them affected their daily existence. From this point of view, it can be said that this work also has a feminist spirit, because Austen shows that women should be valued not only through marriage, but also as individuals. Social stratification is also clearly visible in the work. Society is divided into rich and poor classes, and people's relationships with each other are often determined by their social status. This factor also plays a major role in the issues of marriage and relationships. This situation directly affects the lives of the characters, and some decisions in relation to social pressure and personal choice. In conclusion, Sense and Sensibility is not a simple love story, but a work with a much deeper meaning. It depicts the innermost feelings of a person, the struggle between emotion and logic, financial difficulties and social inequalities, all interwoven. This work makes the reader think and has not lost its relevance even today.

REFERENCES:

1. Austen, J. (1811). Sense and Sensibility. Project Gutenberg. <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/161/old/sense11p.pdf>
2. Encyclopaedia Britannica, Inc. (n.d.). Britannica.com. <https://britannica.com>
3. Landin, M. (2017). Creating the Victorian man: An analysis of the new masculine ideals in Jane Austen's Sense and Sensibility [Degree project, University of Gothenburg]. GUPEA.
4. <https://gupea.ub.gu.se/items/fd288888-0a67-4983-847d-661b519534f0>
5. Brodey, I. S. (2015). Making sense of sensibility. Persuasions, (37), 67–82. <https://share.google/h2rnMPNsPHvRbPaKr>

6. Larraz, J. E. (2015). The feminist influence of Mary Wollstonecraft on
7. Jane Austen's Sense and Sensibility [Bakalavr bitiruv ishi, Universidad de Zaragoza]. Zagan Repositorio Institucional. <https://zagan.unizar.es/record/31963/files/TAZ-TFG-2015-1706.pdf?version=1>
8. Kusumawardhani, M., & Rahayu, E. Y. (2020). Women independence in Jane Austen's Sense and Sensibility as a feminism study. DBB, 15(1), 40–51. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/5739/ac10730af12bfe6b52e97256e5f2b88621ab.pdf>
9. Shubinsky, D. (1999). Sense and Sensibility: An eighteenth-century narrative. Persuasions On-Line, 20(1). <https://jasna.org/persuasions/on-line/vol20no1/shubinsky.html>
10. Zhou, W. (2016). Women on the road: Women in patriarchal society in Sense and Sensibility. English Language and Literature Studies, 6(3), 70–75. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ells.v6n3p70>
11. McKillop, A. D. (1957). The context of Sense and Sensibility. Rice University. <https://repository.rice.edu/handle/1911/10173>
12. Hanna, I. D. (2016). An analysis of the main characters' conflicts in Jane Austen novel entitled "Sense and Sensibility". Wacana Didaktika, 4(2), 156–162. https://www.academia.edu/99324424/an_Analysis_of_The_Main_Characters_Conflicts_in_Jane_Austen_Novel_Entitled_SENSE_AND_SENSIBILITY